

THE EFFECTS OF USING RECYCLED SAND WITH CUSTOMIZED GRANULOMETRY IN LIME-CEMENT MASONRY MORTARS

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ABSTRACT

Efficient reduction of waste through reuse and recycling of materials is one of the integral concepts aiding the society in achieving sustainable development goals. While construction and demolition waste accounts for a large part of wastage produced by human activity, its recycling is still hindered by the inherent heterogeneity of demolished and crushed waste material. And while coarse recycled concrete aggregates are being applied in the production of new construction materials and infrastructure, the simultaneously generated fine aggregate fraction is yet to find a suitable high-value application. Even further problems lie within materials that have not been selectively sorted after construction and demolition, the so-called mixed waste. Hence, this study is dedicated to exploring the possibilities of using such fractions of recycled concrete and recycled mixed waste as complete substitution of traditional aggregates in masonry mortar production in order to reduce the environmental impacts attributed to natural sand extraction and use. The experimental programme aims to compare recycled concrete and recycled mixed waste sands against raw quartz-based sand in two scenarios – firstly considering materials as they are, and secondly when fine aggregate granulometry is customized to fit a desired curve to achieve superior particle packing and subsequently, mortar properties. The results of the study reveal potential to achieve superior masonry mortar performance in both fresh and hardened states by fully substituting natural sand with recycled mixed waste aggregates.

Keywords: *Recycled aggregates, Masonry mortars, Concrete waste, Mixed waste, Custom sand.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Aggregates

Reduction of raw materials' use through various reclamation and recycling routes is undoubtedly an integral part of the ongoing effort to promote sustainable development within the construction industry. As building activities generate enormous amounts of waste, its recycling addresses a multi-faceted problem of not only the high use of natural resources, but also the economic, social and environmental implications of occupying land to store the said waste [1]. In recent decades, the use of recycled coarse concrete aggregates has increased as a consequence of high-quality recycled material generation [2], but the utilization of fine aggregate fraction still remains limited [3]. Even greater reuse constraints stem from the mixed composition of construction and demolition waste (CDW), generated as a result of insufficient and in some cases, impossible waste sorting practice. However, the sustainability issues associated with natural sand mining are pushing for robust solutions through effective recycled sand applications [4].

1.2. Masonry mortars

One potential use case for the recycled sand is in lime-cement mortars for masonry. Often non-structural and exposed to less severe environments when compared to concrete structures, masonry mortars could accommodate relatively large amounts of recycled materials without critical downturn in their properties, as demonstrated previously [5, 6, 7, 8]. The present study aims to showcase which performance-related changes could be expected when raw quartz-based sand (QS) is fully substituted with recycled concrete and recycled mixed waste fine aggregates, RCFA and RMFA, respectively. Simultaneously, the granulometry of all aggregates is adjusted in an attempt to enhance both fresh and hardened mortar properties.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Binders

CL90S air lime conforming to EN 459-1 [9] was paired with CEM II / A-L 32.5 R Portland-limestone cement as specified in EN 197-1 [10].

2.2. Raw and recycled aggregates

Quartz-based natural sand, recycled concrete sand and recycled mixed sand were used in this study. Both recycled concrete and recycled mixed fine aggregates were sourced from CDW recycling and processing companies in Belgium. Recycled concrete aggregates were BENOR-certified [11] for use in structural applications, but the specifics of original structures prior to demolition is unknown. Likewise, mixed waste aggregates also originated from unknown sources, although the presence of concrete, mortar, brick, ceramics, glass and metals was confirmed via visual inspection.

Original particle size distributions (PSD) of the three aggregate types and a custom PSD are presented in Figure 2. The latter granulometric curve was selected based on previous experience and formulated through manual sieving and recombination of the relevant fractions (and addition of quartz filler to increase the fines' content of quartz sand) to ensure a combination of desirable fresh behavior and superior hardened mortar performance compared to original PSD aggregate mortars.

Figure 2. Original granulometry of QS, RCFA and RMFA obtained by sieving and custom granulometry curve.

2.3. Mortars and their properties

Mortars were prepared according to the mix design presented in Table 1. Typical 1:1:6 lime-cement-aggregate formulation was selected based on its general-purpose applicability in masonry construction [12, 13]. Main target was the fresh cohesiveness and workability of mortars made with customized granulometry aggregates, but the same proportions were used in the case of original aggregates to aid the comparison.

Table 1. Composition of mortars – based on 1000 g of dry mortar constituents

Mortar type	Lime:cement:aggregate ratio by volume	Mass of lime (g)	Mass of cement (g)	Mass of aggregates (g)	Mass of water (g)	Water-binder ratio
QS	1:1:6	43.8	98.0	858.2	170.2	1.2
RCFA	1:1:6	52.6	117.7	829.7	272.5	1.6
RMFA	1:1:6	52.6	117.7	829.7	255.5	1.5

Mortars were mixed based on the standard procedure [14] and whilst in fresh state, were tested for flow [15], water retention [16], air content [17] and bulk density [18].

Mechanical strength of mortars was tested in accordance with standard procedures [19]. Other hardened properties include open porosity [20] and capillary water absorption [21].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Fresh mortar properties

Measured fresh properties of mortars are presented in Table 2. Evidently, both types of recycled aggregates induce high water demand in mortars when the content of fines is increased though custom granulometry formulation. However, the same amount of water used in recycled mortars with original PSD of their aggregates results in a substantial increase of flow due to the lack of highly-absorbent fines. Opposite, yet less pronounced effect is observed in quartz sand formulation, where the presence of fine quartz filler actually increases the flowability. Water retention and bulk density are influenced by aggregate sizing only slightly, while air content tends to be lower in mortars made with customized sand.

Table 2. Fresh properties of mortars with natural and recycled aggregates, custom and original granulometry.

q	Granulometry	Flow [mm]	Water retention [%]	Bulk density [kg/m ³]	Air content [%]
QS	Custom	174.5	88.6%	2058.1	4.2%
	Original	168.3	89.1%	1984.4	6.8%
RCFA	Custom	175.5	88.1%	1790.9	6.4%
	Original	222.6	79.9%	1779.0	6.9%
RMFA	Custom	170.0	89.5%	1886.6	5.0%
	Original	207.3	83.3%	1860.1	5.9%

3.2. Mechanical strength, porosity and water absorption

Based on the results showcased in Figure 3, both flexural and compressive strengths of all mortars (except for flexural strength of QS at 8 days) were positively impacted by the use of customized sand granulometry. The largest effect was observed in recycled mixed aggregate mortars, which surpassed even natural aggregate mortars in mechanical performance.

Capillary water absorption and open porosity of mortars was tested on 28-day mortar samples. The results are presented in Figure 4. Water absorption curves reveal that RCFA mortars had the highest water absorption coefficient and absorption capacity, possibly attributed to the highest open porosity values. Contrarily, RMFA mortars exhibited slowest initial water absorption out of the three aggregate types, but water absorption capacity was nonetheless higher than for QS mortar, potentially explained by its lowest open porosity. The latter property was also higher in the case of custom granulometries for all aggregate types, although surprisingly, water absorption properties were not significantly influenced by this.

Figure 3. Flexural and compressive strength of mortars at the ages of 8 days (8D) and 28 days (28D) for both original (O) and customized (C) aggregate granulometries.

Figure 4. Capillary water absorption over time, supplemented by capillary absorption coefficients and open porosities.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Present work demonstrates the potential use case for recycled fine aggregates. The main outcomes of this study are summarized as follows:

- Full natural sand substitution by recycled sand is possible in masonry mortars.
- Recycled mixed aggregate mortars have demonstrated performance, superior not only to that of recycled concrete aggregate mortars, but even of natural quartz sand mortars.
- Customized aggregate granulometry could be used to alter fresh mortar properties to produce a more cohesive, homogeneous and workable mix and improve hardened properties by increasing the mechanical performance. Water absorption remains unaffected even though total porosity is increased compared to original granulometries.

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